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Context Recognition for the Application of Visual Privacy

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Abstract

The population of the world is aging. Studies show that in few decades there will be strong demographic changes which leads to an increase of older people population and triples the current number of over 85 years old people (Padilla-López, 2015). It is expected that more and more older people will be in need of professional healthcare, which will become a burden to families, healthcare systems and the society, so may rise various societal issues.

One of the promising ways to tackle healthcare challenges is Ambient Assisted Living (AAL). AAL systems are intended to be a constant part of the everyday life of older people and aim to improve people's life quality, well-being and safety, while preserving their autonomy (Climent-Pérez, 2020). By taking advantage of information and communication technologies, a variety of sensors can be integrated into home environments and lives of older people, from wearable health sensors (e.g. smart watches, glasses, heart rate sensors) to environmental sensors such as cameras, to detect risks and provide support. Visual components and video cameras are especially important in the context of AAL, since they are the most directed and natural way to record events and situations and also provide rich information (Padilla-López, 2015). Their importance and efficiency have massively increased

by the recent advances in intelligent systems and computer vision technologies so they can be utilized in automatic interpretation of the visual data, smart monitoring, and automatic human lifelogging. However, while cameras in public places have been tolerated, there are serious privacy issues and trust concerns for utilizing them in private spaces, since they enable the acquisition of a huge quantity of information that can be easily interpreted by unauthorized viewers. Therefore, the development of privacy aware video-based applications needs to consider "privacy by design" since early stages. Furthermore, "privacy-by-context" (Padilla-López, 2015) approach is proposed which trades off privacy preservation and image understanding according to the context of the video. In such setups, users can adapt privacy to their preferences in different situations.

In order to achieve this goal, a reliable video context recognition system is a necessity. The focus of this work is to deploy the latest achievements in computer vision research in conjunction with studies on psychological aspects of privacy to develop a user-tailored adaption of visual AAL technologies fulfilling relevant needs and wishes, as well as taking into account existing concerns and fears. The context extracted from such system, should provide enough information to empower people to modify it to their preferences. Therefore, the first stage is to define privacy variables such as: observer, activity, appearance, location. A visualization setup will be applied to the original image according to the user preferences and the ongoing context in the video. There are various methods and filters which can come to aid regarding concealing sensitive information. Using these filters in combination with context information can guarantee user privacy (Padilla-López, 2015). This work varies from dataset creation (Hashemifard, 2022) to segmentation and recognition systems and user studies regarding different variables. Also, some of the most important variables are tackled. For example, regarding the appearance, a nudity recognition system is proposed to detect unwanted body parts whenever exposed. Utilizing the latest deep learning methods in semantic segmentation and with advances in human body parts detection, an exposure map of body is obtained and some of the most important problems such as different illumination and skin tones are tackled (Hashemifard, 2024). By combining them with user studies and preferences, a level-based nudity recognition system is proposed, which can provide different visualizations for different situations in order to choose from (Maidhof, 2022). For activity recognition, daily activities and events in home environment are the most relevant and are taken into account. These activities can include normal behaviour such as drinking and sleeping, and also important events such as falling (Hashemifard, 2023), choking or other health problems. For all the variables the sensitivity of the system is adjusted according to the location and desired privacy presets. This task has been done using the advancements in deep learning techniques, prior knowledge about the objects involved in different activities and human poses in different activities. In the end, by merging the findings in each separate module and developing a

comprehensive context recognition system, a privacy-by-context system for preserving visual privacy can be achieved.

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References

- Climent-Pérez, P., Spinsante, S., Mihailidis, A., & Florez-Revuelta, F. (2020). A review on video-based active and assisted living technologies for automated lifelogging. *Expert Systems with Applications*, *139*, 112847.
- Hashemifard, K., Climent-Perez, P., & Florez-Revuelta, F. (2024). Weakly supervised human skin segmentation using guidance attention mechanisms. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, *83*(10), 31177-31194.
- Hashemifard, K., & Florez-Revuelta, F. (2022, May). From garment to skin: the visual skin segmentation dataset. In *International conference on image analysis and processing* (pp. 59-70). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Hashemifard, K., Florez-Revuelta, F., & Lacey, G. (2023). A Fallen Person Detector with a Privacy-Preserving Edge-AI Camera.
- Maidhof, C., Hashemifard, K., Offermann, J., Ziefle, M., & Florez-Revuelta, F. (2022, June). Underneath your clothes: a social and technological perspective on nudity in the context of AAL technology. In *Proceedings of the 15th international conference on Pervasive technologies related to assistive environments* (pp. 439-445).
- Padilla-López, J. R., Chaaoui, A. A., Gu, F., & Flórez-Revuelta, F. (2015). Visual privacy by context: proposal and evaluation of a level-based visualisation scheme. *Sensors*, *15*(6), 12959-12982.
- Padilla-López, J. R., Chaaoui, A. A., & Flórez-Revuelta, F. (2015). Visual privacy protection methods: A survey. *Expert Systems with Applications*, *42*(9), 4177-4195.